

TABLE 1—O-ALKYLATION OF HYDROXYCOUMARINS WITH ALKYL HALIDES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Anion	Alkylating agent	Reaction time h	Yield %	M.p.* °C
	CH ₃ I	6	99	157 (159) ^a
	C ₆ H ₅ I	8	96	95
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl	10	99	85
	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	10	100	102
	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH ₂ I	10	96	82
	CH ₃ I	6	99	124 (124) ^b
	C ₆ H ₅ I	8	96	185 (186) ^b
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl	8	90	110
	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	6	96	100
	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH ₂ I	10	90	88
	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ I	10	95	92

*Literature value in parenthesis. ^aJ. M. KAUFFMAN, *Appl. Opt.*, 1981, 19, 3491. ^bRef. 3.

chloride form (Amberlyst A-26) packed in a column was washed with aqueous 5% sodium salt of hydroxycoumarin until complete removal of chloride ion. The resin was then successively washed with water, ethanol and benzene and finally dried *in vacuo* at 50° over phosphorus pentoxide for 12 h. The exchange capacity was determined by passing aqueous 1 N sodium chloride (100 ml) through the resin (0.3 g) in a column. The amount of hydroxycoumarin anion in the eluent was titrated with 0.01 N hydrochloric acid using methyl orange as indicator. The product I contains 1.2 mmol hydroxycoumarin per g of resin and product II 1.4 mmol hydroxy coumarin per g of resin.

Alkylation procedure: Amberlyst A-26 hydroxycoumarin anion form (containing 5 mmol hydroxycoumarin) in methanol (15 ml) was stirred with an appropriate alkyl halide (5.01 mmol) in a stoppered flask. After completion of the reaction the resin was removed by filtration and washed with methanol. The distillation of the solvent furnished corresponding alkylated product in quantitative yield in essentially pure form. The products were characterised by comparison of the melting points, ir and nmr spectra with those of authentic samples. The resin used may, in all cases, be easily regenerated by washing with hydrochloric acid.

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Substituted 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-III. Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 1,8-Naphthyridine Derivatives

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1,8-Naphthyridine derivatives have been reported to possess antibacterial¹⁻⁶ and antimalarial^{7,8} activities. Nalidixic acid (1-ethyl-3-carboxy-7-methyl-1,8-naphthyridin-4-one) has been found to be particularly effective against gram-negative bacteria⁹ found in chronic urinary tract infections. Various 2,3-disubstituted-1,8-naphthyridines have been found to be associated with diuretic activity^{10,11}. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a series of unreported 2-substituted-1,8-naphthyridines and test them for their biological activity.

The present communication deals with a one-step synthesis of 2-aryl-1,8-naphthyridines (2), involving the Friedlander condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with arylmethyl ketones in glacial acetic acid with a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid. The same reaction was also carried out in alcohol medium with a few drops of piperidine. The yields are better under acid conditions. The structures of these compounds have been established by elemental analyses and spectral data. The ir spectra of 2 showed bands at 1 600 (C=N), 1 590, 1 540, 1 420, 1 300 and 800 cm⁻¹. The mass spectra of 2 exhibited strong molecular ion peaks consistent with their elemental analyses. The mass spectra of 2-*p*-chloro-

phenyl and 2-nitrophenyl 2 showed strong M^+ peaks at m/z 240 and 251, respectively. The mass spectrum of 2 (R=*p*-Cl.C₆H₄) showed strong M^+ peaks at m/z 240 (M^+ , 84%), 239 ($M^+ - H$, 3%), 205 ($M^+ - Cl$, 10), 204 ($M^+ - Cl - H$, 17), 179 ($M^+ - Cl - C_6H_5$, 10), 178 ($M^+ - Cl - HCN$, 12), 177 (204 - HCN, 17), 152 (179 - HCN, 9), 151 (12), 103 (9), 102 (25), 77 (11),

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-1,8-NAPHTHYRIDINES (2)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N%	
					Found/	(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	116	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂	13.65	(13.59)
2.	4-Methylphenyl	147	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂	12.81	(12.72)
3.	4-Methoxyphenyl	148	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	11.98	(11.87)
4.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	188	78	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	12.70	(12.61)
5.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	254	79	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	12.76	(12.61)
6.	3-Nitrophenyl	219	90	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	16.78	(16.73)
7.	4-Nitrophenyl	263	85	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	16.80	(16.73)
8.	4-Bromophenyl	217	87	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ Br	9.74	(9.83)
9.	2-Pyridyl	148	93	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃	20.35	(20.29)
10.	3-Pyridyl	142	90	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃	20.41	(20.29)
11.	4-Pyridyl	168	92	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃	20.39	(20.29)
12.	2-Naphthyl	165	86	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂	10.99	(10.94)
13.	1-Naphthyl	134	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂	11.01	(10.94)
14.	4-Chlorophenyl	202	92	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ Cl	11.86	(11.67)
15.	2-Hydroxy-4-chlorophenyl	161	82	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	10.50	(10.30)
16.	2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl	190	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	11.79	(11.86)
17.	2-Hydroxy-5-nitrophenyl	240	80	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	15.70	(15.73)
18.	Biphenyl	186	83	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂	9.91	(9.93)
19.	2-Furyl	146	90	C ₁₃ H ₈ N ₂ O	14.18	(14.29)
20.	2-Thienyl	133	92	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₂ S	13.31	(13.20)

* All compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C and H.

** Solvents for crystallisation: Sl. no. 1,2-cyclohexane; 5-ethylacetate; 7,19-chloroform; 8,12,14,18-ethanol; 16,17-aqueous acetic acid, and benzene for the rest.

76 (26) and 75 (27). The pmr spectrum of 2 (R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄) in CDCl₃ showed two multiplets centred at δ 8.5 and 9.3 assigned to C-5 and C-7 protons, respectively. The protons at C-3, C-4 and C-6 on naphthyridine framework appeared along with four aromatic protons as a complex multiplet at δ 7.5-8.3. Finally, the formation of 2 was confirmed by the synthesis of 2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine by the method of Hawes and Wibberley¹³. Physical data of these compounds are recorded in Table 1.

The condensation of acetylacetone with 1 in a 1:2 molar ratio in ethanol in presence of a few drops of piperidine gives 2-methyl-3-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-1,8-naphthyridine (4). The formation of the same compound was confirmed by adopting an alternate method involving the Friedlander condensation of 2-methyl-3-acetyl-1,8-naphthyridine (3) with 1 under the same conditions. The ir spectrum of 4 exhibited strong band at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The spectrum also showed bands at 1550,

1500, 1370, 920 and 850 cm⁻¹. The pmr spectrum in CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆ resonated a three proton singlet at δ 3.1 assigned to methyl group. The C-7 protons on both the naphthyridine moieties appeared as multiplet centred at δ 9.5. The remaining seven protons appeared as a complex multiplet at δ 7.6-8.5. The mass spectrum of 4 showed strong M⁺ peaks at *m/z* 272 (M⁺, 72%), 271 (M⁺ - H, 100), 245 (M⁺ - H - C₂H₅, 15), 244 (M⁺ - H - HCN, 12), 219 (7), 218 (11), 217 (12), 192 (8), 191 (7), 142 (4), and 129 (16).

Antibacterial activity. Twelve compounds of the series were evaluated for their bacterial activity against *Bacillus megaterium* (gram +ve) and *Proteus vulgaris* (gram -ve), using the filter paper disc method¹³. Two different concentrations of twelve compounds (360 and 600 μg/disc) were prepared and 25 Whatman filter paper (No. 1) discs (6 mm dia) were dipped and the solutions were allowed to evaporate. The paper discs with different com-

pounds were placed aseptically on petriplates containing nutrient agar seeded with different bacteria and incubated for 72 h at $37 \pm 1^\circ$. At the end of the incubation period, the zone of growth inhibition was measured and expressed in mm. At least 10 paper discs were observed and repeated twice. The results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 2

Sl. no.	Concn. $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$	Inhibition zone (mm)	
		<i>B. megaterium</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>
1.	360	1.2	3.0
	600	2.0	4.0
2.	360	1.0	3.2
	600	2.2	3.6
3.	360	—	3.0
	600	2.0	4.8
4.	360	—	1.0
	600	—	2.8
5.	360	—	—
	600	—	—
6.	360	1.4	—
	600	2.0	1.8
7.	360	—	—
	600	—	2.0
8.	360	—	1.0
	600	—	2.0
9.	360	—	—
	600	1.3	1.0
10.	360	—	—
	600	1.0	1.2
11.	360	1.0	1.0
	600	1.4	1.8
12.	360	—	—
	600	1.0	1.0

(—)=No inhibition.

* Referred to as in Table 1.

Anthelmintic activity: Three selected compounds (sl. no. 9, 10 and 11) were screened for their anthelmintic activity using the method of Seifter¹⁴ on five Amphistome parasites, *Fischoederius cobboldii*, *Fischoederius elongatus*, *Gastrothylax crumenifer*, *Cotylophoron cotylophorum* and *Paramphistomum cervi*. All the three compounds exhibited helminthecidal property against all the organisms tested. However, the degree of toxicity varied with the compound. Compound 9 was found to be more effective in comparison with the other two, but it was less effective than the drug mebendazole. It was suggested that 80% inhibition of glucose uptake was possible as observed by the compound 9. The other two compounds (sl. no. 10 and 11) showed an inhibition of 76%. Compared to mebendazole these have very less activity. It is concluded from these results that 2-(pyridyl)-1,8-naphthyridines do have the anthelmintic property. The degree of toxicity is found to depend upon the position of the pyridyl group.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes in sulphuric acid-bath and are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds was checked by

tlc. Ir spectra were run in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian 60 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference, and the mass spectra on a varian MAT CM-7 instrument at 70 eV.

2-Aryl-1,8-naphthyridine (2): A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1; 0.1 mol) and appropriate aryl methyl ketone (0.1 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid for 3 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent to give 2 (Table 1).

2-Methyl-3-acetyl-1,8-naphthyridine (3): To an equimolar mixture of 1 (0.1 mol) and acetylacetone (0.1 mol) was added ethanol (20 ml) and a few drops of piperidine. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, and cooled. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (90%), m.p. 146° (lit.¹⁵ $146-7^\circ$).

2-Methyl-3-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-1,8-naphthyridine (4): Method-A: 1 (0.2 mol) and acetylacetone (0.1 mol) were refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of a few drops of piperidine for 12 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool. The solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from benzene, (65%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 74.90; H, 4.38; N, 20.55. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires: C, 75.00; H, 4.41; N, 20.59%).

Method-B: An equimolar mixture of 1 (0.1 mol) and 3 (0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, and the separated solid filtered and recrystallised from benzene.

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**Chemical Examination of the Leaves of
Juniperus bermudiana Linn.
(Cupressaceae)**

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JUNIPERUS bermudiana Linn. (Syn. *J. virginiana*) was examined only for its biflavonoid contents¹. We have undertaken a thorough investigation of *J. bermudiana* leaves. Dried and powdered leaves (1.5 kg) procured from F. R. I., Dehradun (India), were extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone. Petroleum ether and benzene extracts were combined and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed over Si-gel column affording the following compounds. Identification is based on spectral studies and also comparison of m.ps. and spectral data with those reported.

n-Hexane elution : It gave a white crystalline compound (150 mg), m.p. 63°, M^+ 408, analysed for $C_{29}H_{60}$; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 880 and 1 465 cm^{-1} ; m/e 408 (M^+), 379, 350, 336, 322, 308, 297 and 157; τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (60H, s); confirmed its identity as nonacosane (lit.² m.p. 63.6-64°).

Further elution with the same solvent provided an another crystalline compound (80 mg), m.p. 84°, M^+ 429, $C_{29}H_{60}O$; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (OH), 2 890, 1 460, 1 370, 1 330, 1 120, 1 080, 1 055, 850 and 710 cm^{-1} ; m/e 424 (M^+), 409 ($M-CH_3$), 406 ($M-H_2O$), 378 ($M-H_2O-C_2H_4$) and 297 ($M-C_9H_{19}$), and peaks of masses separated by 14 units (CH_2) with increasing intensity (characteristics of long chain alcohol); τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (59H, s) and 7.55 (1H, s); suggested it to be 1-nonacosanol (lit.³ m.p. 84-5°); further confirmed by acetylation with Ac_2O-Py , τ (CCl_4) 8.75 (59H, s) and 8.35 (3H, s, 1-OAc).

Petrol benzene (7 : 3) elution : It afforded a LB positive white solid which on crystallisation (petrol-ether) yielded needles (70 mg), m.p. 165° (lit. m.p.

167°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 720, 1 690, 1 658, 1 640, 1 004, 914, 880, 830 cm^{-1} ; τ ($CDCl_3$) 9.01 (3H, s), 8.94 (3H, s), 8.78 (3H, s), 5.23, 5.00, 4.68 and 4.13 (m). Spectral data were found identical in all respects with those reported for sandaracopimeric acid^{4,5}.

Ethyl acetate extract : On further purification by solvent treatment and column chromatography followed by preparative tlc yielded three biflavonoids labelled as JBI, JBII and JBIII. Each was analysed separately by methylation and acetylation followed by pmr determination and found identical in m.p., chromatographic and spectral data with the reported biflavonoids¹.

Acetone extract : The brown residue on purification by paper chromatography (n-BuOH-AcOH- H_2O , 4 : 1 : 5) yielded a yellow compound, m.p. 181°, R_f 0.80. On hydrolysis (10% HCl), it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315°, identified as quercetin by comparing R_f , m.p. and shade in uv light of its methyl ether⁷, and a sugar. The sugar was confirmed as rhamnose by pc (n-BuOH-AcOH- H_2O , 4 : 1 : 5, R_f 0.31); n-BuOH- $EtOH-H_2O$, 4 : 1 : 2, R_f 0.36; yellow brown colour with aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying reagent. The glycosidic linkage was established by methylation ($Me_2SO_4-K_2CO_3$) followed by acid hydrolysis. The partial methyl ether, m.p. 195° obtained, was acetylated (Ac_2O-Py) to give an acetate, m.p. 159°. Pmr spectrum showed the oxygenation pattern of quercetin with one acetoxy at τ 7.71 and four methoxyls at τ 6.18-6.23. Mass spectrum of the partial methyl ether provided main peaks at m/e 358 (M^+ , 100%), 343 ($M-CH_3$), 329 ($M-HCO$), 180 and 179 (RDA fragments). The fragments m/e 329 and 179 confirmed OH group at C-3. Bathochromic shift⁸ of 55 nm (in band I) with $AlCl_3$ further confirmed OH at C-3. The glycosidation was therefore at C-3. The structure of the compound was thus assigned as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside⁹. This is the first report of the occurrence of these compounds in the family Cupressaceae.

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